

PROCESSING AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF NOVEL WOOD FIBRE COMPOSITES FOAMS

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SUMMARY

Wood fibre reinforced polylactic acid (PLA) composite foams have been successfully produced using supercritical carbon dioxide. A significant increase of specific properties, both stiffness and strength, was achieved by adding 5-10 wt% wood fibres. The experimental stiffness was comparable with a superposed micromechanical model for a three phase fibre reinforced foam. These first results on the integration of wood fibres into cellular PLA polymer are very encouraging.

Keywords: polylactic acid (PLA), wood fibres, foams, supercritical processing, cellular composites

INTRODUCTION

The development of cellular polymers and composites has experienced a very large increase in recent years in many applications as biomedical implants [1], packaging, insulation panels or sandwich core. These materials are particularly important to attain significant weight reductions and have interesting properties compared to bulk materials, e.g. higher impact strength, toughness, thermal conductivity, etc. It would be desirable to develop cellular composites with similar or better properties than the current foams available on the market but that are biodegradable, compostable and based on renewable resources.

One very promising polymer is polylactic acid (PLA) derived from renewable resources such as corn or sugar canes [2]. Until the 1980s, the high production costs limited its use to the biomedical field but with processing improvement and lower production cost, PLA has become more and more competitive compared to other petroleum-based polymers. To improve mechanical properties, PLA can be reinforced with fibres. In contrast to man-made fibres, wood fibres are renewable, biodegradable and recyclable. Efforts have been made to develop foams with microfibrillar cellulose reinforcing the cell wall [3]. The potential of wood fibre reinforced foams has not been investigated to the same extent until now. One argument is that wood fibres are too large compared

with the cell size to provide any tangible reinforcement. This study shows that wood fibres indeed can serve as reinforcement, and improve the mechanical properties.

Polymer and composite foams can be produced in both batch and continuous processes (such as extrusion and injection moulding) using either physical or chemical foaming agents. In a batch process, materials are first saturated with the foaming agent under certain temperature and pressure. A thermodynamic instability is created in the polymer. The quick pressure release leads to the nucleation and growth of cells. The structure is fixed by cooling. The critical processing parameters affecting the microstructure are the saturation time, the foaming temperature, the saturation pressure, depressurisation and cooling rates. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is often considered as a promising “green solvent” alternative to noxious organic solvents and chlorofluorocarbons [4]. It can have the properties of supercritical fluids which, above a critical temperature and pressure, display a density similar to that of a liquid with a diffusivity and viscosity similar to that of a gas. Supercritical CO₂ has been used to produce foam in batch processing condition of e.g. polyethylene (HDPE) and polypropylene (PP) filled with wood particles [5]. Fillers are known to act as nucleating agent and change the melt viscosity. Moreover fillers influence the microstructure and thus the mechanical and thermal properties of the foams [6]. For instance, HDPE and PP foams with wood particle fillers displayed an increase in both stiffness and strength, at lower cost [5]. However these improvements in mechanical properties are usually accompanied by a reduction in both ductility and impact resistance.

The aim of this work is to experimentally study wood fibre reinforced PLA foams that are batch produced using supercritical CO₂. The idea is to gain increased knowledge on the processing routes and attainable properties of these composite foams. For a given processing path, foams with various wood fibre contents and fibre treatments are studied. The foam morphology, determined through microscopic observation, and the mechanical behaviour, measured by compression tests, are investigated. Results of the mechanical tests are compared with predictions of a micromechanical model.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

PLA fibres (PLA01, N.I. Teijin Shoji Co. Ltd., Japan) and fully bleached commercial birch fibres were used to produce commingled preforms which were subsequently foamed using supercritical CO₂. The wood fibres were treated with (i) butyl tetracarboxylic acid (BTCA) and (ii) with BTCA and an additional surfactant Na₂HP0₄ composed of a positively charged head and a negatively charged tail. The BTCA can be used as cellulose cross-linking agent, which introduces cross-links inside the cell wall leading to increased fibre stiffness [7]. With the surfactant the fibres become negatively charged, an effect which is expected to hinder the wood fibres to aggregate by reducing their ability to form hydrogen bonds.

The characteristic of the fibres is given in Table 1 in terms of the fibre length l , diameter d , and aspect ratio $\alpha = l/d$.

Table 1. Characteristics of the PLA and wood fibres. The dimensions of the wood fibres were obtained with a FiberMaster measuring system [8].

Fibre	Treatment	Code	l (mm)	d (μm)	α
PLA	-	PL01	5	-	-
Birch	-	UWF	2.34	28.8	81
Birch	Cross linked with BTCA	CLWF	2.04	28.3	72
Birch	Cross linked with BTCA and treated with Na_2HPO_4	SCWF	2.34	29.4	80

Preform preparation and supercritical foaming

Preforms were made by commingling PLA and wood fibres in the wet state, in a way which resembles slurry processing used in paper production. The resulting wet preforms were dried on absorbent paper, and then further consolidated in an oven at 175°C for 30 minutes before being pressed at 40 bars for 5 minutes. The wood fibre content in the mat was varied, 1%, 5%, 10% and 20% by weight. The orientation of the wood fibres in the preforms is expected to be in plane uniform. The preforms were oven dried freely, at 60°C for at least 24 hours before further processing.

Foaming was carried out in a high-pressure chamber (Autoclave France), connected to a back-pressure regulator and a water cooling system, using supercritical CO_2 (Messer Schweiz AG, Switzerland). The preforms were stacked with the fibres being uniformly distributed in a plane perpendicular to the rise direction of the foams. The processing temperature, i.e. the saturation pressure (185°C), was chosen to be about 20°C higher than the melting point of the PLA fibres. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC Q100, TA Instruments) was used to determine the melting point of the different preforms. The melting temperature varied between 165°C and 166.3°C for all wood fibre types and contents, i.e. showing that the wood fibres had very little influence. The saturation pressure (200 bar), saturation time (10 min) as well as depressurization and cooling rate (initial rates about 13 bar/s and 5°C/s, respectively) were chosen to obtain as high initial porosity, i.e. low density, as possible [9].

Mechanical testing and microscopy

Compression test were made on cubic specimens ($10 \times 10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^3$) in three directions, as schematically shown in Figure 1, the foaming direction (III), i.e. direction of foam expansion, and two directions perpendicular to it, i.e. the transverse directions (I and II). Compression tests on the cubes were carried out using a universal testing machine (UTS Test System, Germany), with a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. A minimum of 5 specimens were tested in each direction, whenever possible. The compressive modulus, E_c , elastic collapse stress, σ_Y , and strain, ε_Y , were determined from recorded load and displacement curves. The apparent foam density, ρ^* , was determined by weighing and measuring the volume of each sample.

Figure 1. : Schematic representation prepared specimens in relation to the foaming (rise) direction of the sample.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to examine the microstructure of the wood fibre composite foams. Razor blade cut samples were carbon coated with a high vacuum carbon coater (Cressington 208) and were observed with a microscope (Philips XL30) in secondary electron mode at an accelerating voltage of 3 kV. Two specimens from each sample were observed for each of the three perpendicular spatial directions. Image analysis was carried out using the open source software ImageJ [10], which offers the possibility of extracting quantitative information from the porous structure. The Feret's diameter, i.e. the measured distance between theoretical parallel lines that are drawn tangent to the cell profile in the micrograph, was used as a measure of the average cell size. This measure can also be used to obtain an estimate of the average cell wall thickness and cell density together with the foam porosity [11].

MICROMECHANICAL MODELLING

The mechanical properties of two phase foams (polymer/cell) can be related to the foam density, whilst the cellular nature of the microstructure determines the mode of failure under stress [12]. In this work it is desirable to analyse the three-phase foam (polymer/fibre/cell) and predict the reinforcement effect of the wood fibres. It has previously been shown that the concept of laminate analogy can be used to predict the modulus of high density reinforced foams [13]. A similar approach will be used here and will be briefly described in the following. The fundamental idea and assumption is that the foam can be treated as homogenous material with the effective properties of a foam. It is further assumed the wood fibres are randomly distributed in the plane with normal direction III.

The laminate analogy approach is based on modelling composites reinforced by nonaligned discontinuous fibres by using the classical lamination theory for a stack of unidirectional layers, each of which accounts, for one fibre orientation. In this way, the modulus of a wide range of nonaligned short-fibre reinforced composite can be estimated, e.g. [14]. The modulus of a composite with fibres uniformly oriented in-plane can be written like

$$E_c = \frac{U_1^2 - U_4^2}{U_1} \quad (1)$$

where U_1 and U_4 are well known laminate invariants defined as

$$U_1 = \frac{3}{8}Q_{11} + \frac{3}{8}Q_{22} + \frac{1}{4}Q_{12} + \frac{1}{2}Q_{66} \quad (2)$$

$$U_4 = \frac{1}{8}Q_{11} + \frac{1}{8}Q_{22} + \frac{3}{4}Q_{12} - \frac{1}{2}Q_{66} \quad (3)$$

where Q_{11} , Q_{22} , Q_{12} and Q_{66} are components of the stiffness matrix of a laminate with perfectly aligned fibres. These are related to engineering constants as $Q_{11} = E_L/(1 - \nu_{LT}\nu_{TL})$, $Q_{22} = E_T/(1 - \nu_{LT}\nu_{TL})$, $Q_{12} = \nu_{LT}E_T/(1 - \nu_{LT}\nu_{TL})$ and $Q_{66} = G_{LT}$, where $\nu_{TL} = \nu_{LT}E_T/E_L$. The longitudinal and transverse Young's modulus of the lamina are denoted E_L and E_T , respectively. The major Poisson ratio is denoted ν_{LT} and the shear modulus G_{LT} . The properties of the lamina (E_L , E_T , G_{LT} , ν_{LT}) can be obtained from the properties of its constituents (fibre and matrix) using a micromechanical model. The Halpin-Tsai equations [15] can be applied to short fibre composites as

$$\frac{M}{M_m} = \frac{1 + \zeta\eta V_{f1}}{1 - \eta V_{f1}} \quad (4)$$

$$\eta = \frac{(M_f/M_m) - 1}{(M_f/M_m) + \zeta} \quad (5)$$

where M , M_f and M_m represent the moduli, listed in Table 2, which also gives the parameter ζ , and change depending on which lamina modulus is sought. The volume fraction of the wood fibres contained in cell walls of the foam composite is represented by V_{f1} .

Table 2. Parameters given in Equations (4)-(5).

M	M_f	M_m	ζ
E_L	E_{f1}	E_m	$2(l/d)$
E_T	E_{f2}	E_m	2
G_{LT}	G_{f12}	G_m	1

In Table 2 the moduli E_{f1} , E_{f2} , G_{f12} are the anisotropic elastic properties of the wood fibres and E_m , G_m are the matrix properties. In the longitudinal direction of the lamina the parameter ζ depend on the aspect ratio of the fibre, l/d , i.e. the ratio between their

length, l , and diameter, d , which is given in Table 1. The Poisson ratio, ν_{LT} , can be obtained from the rule of mixture,

$$\nu_{LT} = \nu_f V_{f1} + \nu_m (1 - V_{f1}) \quad (6)$$

where ν_{f12} and ν_m are the Poisson ratios of the wood fibres and matrix, respectively. So far, the model described can be applied for any type of short fibre composites with a uniform fibre orientation distribution. To adapt the model to fibre reinforced foams, it is assumed that the matrix material (in Table 2) can be described by the Gibson-Ashby relation [12] for open cell foams

$$E_m = E_{PLA} (1 - V_p)^2 \quad (7)$$

where E_{PLA} is the modulus of solid PLA and V_p is the porosity of the foam. Equations (1)-(7) can now be used to estimate the modulus of short fibre reinforced foams as function of V_p and V_{f1} . It is necessary to know the fibre properties, the matrix properties and the relation between V_p - V_{f1} to be able to predict the foam composite modulus. The relation between V_{f1} and V_p can be written

$$V_{f1} = V_f (1 - V_p) \quad (8)$$

where V_f is the fibre volume fraction in the preform, i.e. before foaming. This can be obtained from the weight fraction W_f as

$$V_f = \frac{\rho_c}{\rho_f} W_f \quad (9)$$

$$\rho_c = \rho_f V_f + \rho_{PLA} (1 - V_f) \quad (10)$$

where ρ_f and ρ_{PLA} are the density of the fibres and solid PLA matrix. The volume fraction of porosity in Equations (7)-(8) is obtained from the relative density as

$$V_p = 1 - \frac{\rho^*}{\rho_c} \quad (11)$$

where ρ^* is the density of the foam composite and ρ_c the density of the bulk composite.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphology

SEM provided qualitative as well as quantitative microstructural data useful for understanding structural formation during processing and building an appropriate micromechanical model.

All foams displayed a rather large dispersion in cell size, in particular the pure PLA foams and the composite foams with 1 wt% wood fibres (see Figure 2 for foams with UWF). No significant impact of wood fibre treatment on cell morphology was seen. The micrographs shown in Figure 2 for foams with UWF can be considered representative for each composition for all surface treatments. The evolution in structure and morphology at higher wood fibre contents can clearly be seen in Figure 2. As the fibre content increased the cell size decreased, although a few large and extremely elongated pores are visible in planes with normal direction I and II. With image analysis an interesting trend was observed, and considering the pure PLA case as separate (homogeneous cell nucleation), an increase in wood fibre content implied smaller cell sizes (measured as the Feret diameter) in all cases, confirmed what was apparent on the micrographs (Figure 2). Again it was not possible to distinguish if wood fibre treatments had a significant effect on the values measured for the cell sizes since all cases were largely comparable, within experimental uncertainty.

Figure 2. Microstructure of foams with UWF for different fibre content. The direction of the normal of the plane of view is indicated, i.e. I-II show a plane in the foaming direction, and III a plane perpendicular to it.

Micrographs in the plane perpendicular to the foaming direction, i.e. normal direction III, revealed significant amounts of fibres, only for fibre contents higher than 1 wt% (Figure 2). It appeared that the fibres had remained in this particular plane and were not considerably disrupted by the foaming. The density of wood fibres was quite impressive and very few fairly regular shaped cells were seen on these planes. Moreover fibres in

foams with up to 10 wt% appeared to be well wetted, none of them sticking out bare and they remained mainly uniformly oriented in the plane perpendicular to the foaming direction. It was clear that for all the foams the fibres mainly stayed in plane I-II. The driving force for cell growth is induced by the pressure difference, between the cell and the external pressure. This force is opposed mainly by the resistance of the material surrounding the cell governed by the elongational viscosity. The wood fibres were randomly oriented in plane I-II, perpendicular to the foaming direction, and create a network of fibres in this plane. It is likely that the cells expand easier in the foaming direction and the perpendicular directions in-between the wood fibre layers, which form a network more difficult to deform. This could also explain the observation of large cells oriented perpendicular to the foaming direction, especially in foams with higher wood fibre content.

The microstructure at high fibre content, 20 wt%, changed. SEM micrographs showed there was too little PLA matrix to perfectly wet all the fibres (Figure 3). Fibres jutting out of the surface of planes with normal in direction I and II were visible, indicating that they have essentially remained in the plane perpendicular to the foaming direction. Figure 3 confirms that the specimens with 20 wt% wood fibres were not foams as the fibres were incompletely impregnated, and the structure resembled more the one of simple fibre mat.

Figure 3. Micrograph of foam with 20 wt% UWF showing insufficient fibre impregnation.

An estimation of the fibre diameter using Figure 3 gives values ranging from 20-30 μm , which are in agreement with the measurements in Table 1. A high degree of orientation similar to the stacking of layers in the commingled preforms before initial compaction was visible. This suggests that the pre-compaction was not sufficient and during heating in the autoclave the preform might expand due to release of internal stresses. This would obviously cause large voids in the preform (as was seen between different wood

fibre layers and perpendicular to the foaming direction) before saturation temperature and pressure are reached in the autoclave. Upon venting the gas will probably follow these fast paths out of the material, not contributing to any cell formation.

The main conclusion from the SEM study is that the presence of wood fibres gave rise to a change in the foam morphology. The foam microstructure was highly inhomogeneous. The preforms had a layered structure and cell formation took place mainly in between the layered wood fibre networks. In many cases it was found that large foam cells or macro-pores were elongated perpendicular to the foaming direction. Generally good wetting of the wood fibres by the PLA matrix was noticed. The wood fibres remained oriented uniformly in the plane perpendicular to the foaming direction as in the preform before the foaming. Addition of 10 wt% wood fibres seemed to be a limit to obtain foams, with the used processing conditions.

Density and mechanical properties

The results of the density measurements are shown against weight fraction of wood fibres in Figure 4. There was an increase in density, for all fibre treatments, from 1 wt% to 10 wt% fibre content. The materials with 20 wt% which cannot be considered as foams had lower densities than the reinforced foams. The decrease in density for foams with 1 wt% wood fibres could be due to increased nucleation but also because of insufficient viscosity which could lead to cell coalescence. The different fibre treatments seem to reduce the density increase. This effect is slightly higher for SCWF which were treated in a way to form a weaker wood fibre network in the preform. This could allow for more foam expansion as compared with CLWF and UWF reinforced foams.

Figure 4. Foam density as function of the weight fraction in the preforms.

Values of the Feret diameter obtained from image analysis were used together with the density data in Figure 4 to approximate the average cell wall thickness. Results showed that average cell wall thicknesses in between boundaries of 15–45 μm , with the overall trend following what has already been seen for density, i.e. increase with wood fibre content. These values are of the same order as the wood fibre sizes. Higher value of the cell wall thickness might reasonably be expected to fully sheath the fibres but, the estimate for has not been found to be much smaller than the fibre dimensions. It was also found that the density of cells is approximately of $4 \cdot 10^4$ cells/ cm^3 , which is comparable to conventional reported values of 10^2 – 10^3 cells/ cm^3 . However, it should be mentioned that the Feret diameters obtained with image analysis were lower than approximate made directly on SEM micrographs, leading to an underestimation of the cell wall thickness and an overestimation of the number of cells.

There was a wide distribution in results of the mechanical tests (cf. Figure 5). This was due to the inhomogeneous microstructure of the foams. The mechanical testing was done on 10 mm sided cubes, and in many cases the largest cell or void was of the order of mm, i.e. above an acceptable threshold of $L = 10D$, that is the size of the specimen L should at least be 10 times higher than cell with the largest diameter D . Therefore results of the mechanical testing should be regarded more qualitative instead of quantitative. Nevertheless, some obvious trends could be established. All foams displayed anisotropic properties. The specific stiffness and strength were significantly higher in direction I and II, for reinforced foams with 5 wt% and 10 wt% fibres. The wood fibres were mainly oriented in the plane of the preforms, and several preforms were stacked on each other in the mould, which explains the marked increase in transverse properties for foam composites.

Figure 5. (a) Specific properties of pure PLA foams (■) foam composites with UWF (×) and CLWF (○).

No significant reinforcement effect was seen as expected in the foaming direction with the exception of the foam composites with 1 wt% fibres. This could be due to processing induced anisotropy, which gives rise to elongated and preferentially oriented cells in the foaming direction (cf. Figure 2). A decrease in specific stiffness and strength in direction III was seen in particular for the foams with 5 wt% fibres. This may be explained by macro-pores oriented perpendicular to the foaming direction (Figure 2) which could lead to a weaker structure.

The results of the mechanical testing for foams with UWF and CLWF in all directions are shown in Figure 5a-b as the specific properties, i.e. E_c / ρ^* vs. σ_Y / ρ^* (Figure 5a) and σ_Y / ρ^* vs. ε_Y (Figure 5b). The density of these foams is shown in Figure 4. The only foams that present a significant increase in specific stiffness and strength as compared with neat PLA foams in Figure 5a are the foams with 5 wt% and 10 wt% fibres in the transverse directions (I and II). In addition, a simultaneous increase in the elastic collapse strain was noticed for foams with 10 wt% fibres (Figure 5b). The foams with CLWF were stiffer and stronger than the corresponding foams with UWF, at 5 wt% but not at 10 wt% fibre content. It has previously been shown that BTCA treated wood fibres have higher stiffness as compared with untreated fibres [14]. Foams with SCWF showed similar properties.

The micromechanical model which superposes the Gibson-Ashby relation [12] and the Halpin-Tsai equations, Equations (1)-(11), was used to predict the stiffness of the foam composites. Input data needed are the relation between foam porosity, Equation (11), and volume fraction of the wood fibres in the preforms, Equation (8), as well as the elastic parameters of the constituents. The Young's modulus of PLA, $E_{PLA} = 2.2$ GPa, was obtained with Equation (7) using experimental data for pure PLA foams in direction I and II. The longitudinal stiffness, E_{f1} , for the UWF and both the treated fibres were taken from Neagu et al. [14], as 35 GPa and 40 GPa, respectively. The Poisson ratios were chosen to $\nu_m = 0.3$ and $\nu_{f12} = 0.3$, and the needed anisotropic properties, $E_{f2}/E_{f1} = 0.125$ and $G_{f12}/E_{f1} = 0.1$, were based on values found in literature [14].

The porosity and fibre volume fraction were worked out using the density data in Figure 4 and Equations (11) and (9) are plotted in Figure 6a. The density values for the PLA and wood fibres in Equation (10) were 1.26 g/cm^3 and 1.5 g/cm^3 , respectively. The materials with 20 wt% were omitted.

Figure 6. (a) Foam porosity versus preform fibre volume fraction (b) Model predictions of the stiffness for foams reinforced with the three different fibre types (continuous lines) and for pure PLA foam (dashed line) compared with experimental data in directions I-II.

Foam porosity as a function of the preform fibre volume fraction showed practically a linear trend (Figure 6a), the porosity decreasing for higher fibre content. The foams with UWF and CLWF showed similar trend, however the slope for SCWF reinforced foams

was lower. The lower slope is the more is the amount of fibres can be added for a given relative density or porosity. It was previously mentioned that the surfactant treated cross linked fibres are less bound and form a weaker network probably allowing for more foam expansion, hence lower relative density (Figure 4) or higher porosity (Figure 6a).

The reinforcement potential increases with increased fibre stiffness (cross linked fibres have higher stiffness) and increased aspect ratio. Even so, the key factor is the relation between, foam porosity and fibre volume fraction in the preform shown in Figure 6a, the higher the slope of the linear relation V_p-V_f is the more reinforcement is obtained.

CONCLUSIONS

Foams with different fibre content and treatment were produced using supercritical CO₂ from a stack of preforms done by a wet process and composed of wood and PLA fibres. The fibres were oriented randomly in-plane and perpendicular to the foaming direction. The addition of fibres had a strong effect on microstructure of the foams. With the processing conditions used in this work the limit of maximal fibre fraction that can be added was 10 wt%.

Reinforced foams were anisotropic and stiffer in the directions where wood fibres were uniformly dispersed than in the foaming direction. No significant difference was observed between the UWF and CLWF reinforced foams. Foams with SCWF had lower relative density, i.e. higher porosity, for the same foam morphology and were easier to expand. The key factor for reinforcement is the relation between, foam porosity (relative density) and fibre volume fraction in the preform.

The foaming conditions have to be adapted for each wood fibre content to obtain foam with the desired porosity. To maximise the reinforcement effect, foams have to be done in a way so the porosity does not decrease to a large extent with increased wood fibre fraction. Changing the viscosity of the matrix and fibre treatment, i.e. like the surfactant treatment used in this study, could help. Another solution could be to make foams with smaller cells and higher cell density, by increasing the cooling rate and depressurization rate.

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